

The Dichotomy Between Data Ownership and Data Utilization: Using Personal Data for the Greater Good

Simon Lin

Imagine a world without suffering. A world where diseases are prevented, accidents predicted, and every single decision made is the best possible choice. Processes and distribution of resources are optimally streamlined, any potential risk minimized and wellbeing just a matter of choice, rather than destiny.

*Life being a function of data and processing power equals this reality.
(AI/ML = Big Data x Computational infrastructure)*

With data privacy and ownership being one of the biggest hundler in this equation we are left with the burning question of the reasons behind. A sober assessment of this matter results in the rationale that acceleration of data collection and sharing in order to optimize technological progress should be prioritized at all costs to achieve global prosperity as soon as possible, however we humans are a testament that life is more than just a sequence of logical events. In this article we are throwing the spotlight onto why data has such a pivotal role moving humanity forward and are exploring the back-end to our problematic front-end attempting to identify the quintessential drivers behind our reluctance to give up personal data as a resource for progress.

1. The Potential Within Data

Big data is a concept discovered in the 1990s, popularized by US computer scientist John Mashey. It describes data that includes data sets with sizes beyond the ability of commonly used software tools to capture, curate, manage, and process data within a tolerable elapsed time¹. Roughly around 2000 the digital age had initiated a rapid increase in collected data by digital storage media.

In order to unlock the full potential of big data two main technologies were required: computing infrastructure and code to run on it.

Computation power. Over the years constant research has progressed in both of these areas, leading eventually to the introduction of the concepts of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) along with ever growing efficiency

1 C. Snijders, U. Matzat, and U.-D. Reips, “‘Big Data’: Big Gaps of Knowledge in the Field of Internet Science”, in «International Journal of Internet Science», 7 (1), p. 1-5. Available at: https://kops.uni-konstanz.de/bitstream/handle/123456789/28647/Snijders_286475.pdf?sequence=2.

of transistor technology. Moore's law describes an empirical relationship that the number of transistors in a dense integrated circuit (IC) doubles about every two years². It basically translates into the prediction of exponential increase in processing power going forward with its plateau to be expected within the next 5 years. However, new concepts such as quantum computing are on the verge of disrupting the status quo and setting the stage for new "laws" to be defined.

While technological advancements in computing technology are uncoupled from data resources, algorithms to process them form the bridge dependent on both data and computing. This enticing love triangle holds arguably humanities future in its hands and probably deserves even more attention and engagement than currently receiving.

2. Discovering Consciousness

Consciousness. The advent of silicon microchips has rapidly changed our world and transformed roles in human society. The description of life had been fundamentally disrupted and with it the perception of consciousness and human cognition in general. While once consciousness was regarded something exclusive, spiritual, and almost in a way mystical, something closely interwoven with the believe of the existence of a soul, transcendence and the unexplainable, after the creation of an artificial processing unit (i.e., central processing unit (CPU)), consciousness seems more explainable and has become a more graspable concept than before. Humanity had become capable of creating something that somehow, at least rudimentarily, emulated an entity possessing the capability of thinking. With the rise of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) and its ambitious ever-growing community of enthusiasts, an alternative belief system has been fostered, attempting to decode the essence of consciousness.

Transcendence. Already the ancient Greek philosopher Socrates had formulated an important hint highlighting the impuissance of human cognition. "I know that I know nothing", which has been and can be interpreted in many ways, however the core of this anecdote points at the fact, that we humans are limited in our capacity for knowledge, and therefore will always be restrained in the quest for the ultimate truth, accepting the fact that there will be mysteries beyond human cognition. This can be seen as the foundation of the incitement to create extra-human cognition to solve the puzzle that lies within ourselves. A puzzle that has perpetually driven the human spirit. Some call it the purpose of life, some the way to enlightenment, some the theory of everything, but ultimately it is the explanation that lies one level above transcendence.

If god created everything, if the big bang was the inception of the universe, what was before, what lies behind the fabric of reality?

² G. E. Moore, "Cramming More Components onto Integrated Circuits", in «Electronics», 38 (8), 1965.

Revolution. Great contemporary thinkers such as Yuval Noah Harari³, have already identified the potential splendour of “artificial intelligence”, whereas developing that sentiment further probably leading to “artificial consciousness”, whereas we have yet failed to clearly define consciousness itself. Harari presents the idea of AI taking over tasks which are currently performed by human intelligence. This concept is nothing we are strangers to, as throughout history humans had been striving to invent technology, which would take over tasks that are exhausting, complex or simply tedious to complete. However, in the case of AI the playground of tasks is slightly different. One can confidently say, considerably more sophisticated and impactful, than any playground before. While the steam engine, as other engines in general, enabled manual work to be automated, “digital engines” have enabled mental work to be taken over and “knowledge workers” to be increasingly replaced. Harari argues that it is an inevitable path we have commenced walking on, in which AI will be able to take over our thinking, believing, liking, our way of living. (Provided humanity survives long enough without facing extortion through its own hands or natural disaster).

In the not so far future AI will know us better than we ourselves will ever be able to, because we humans are limited in our processing prowess – machines hypothetically are not – and we are working tirelessly to prove this hypothesis being true.

Free will. Algorithms already today are suggesting and predicting our favourite music, clothing, interests, and habits. Global companies have built their business models revolving around collecting our personal data and learning from it. In fact, with the inception of social media the business model of understanding human habits and manipulating those, have become a household tool to bring attention to products and optimizing sales conversion. The whole retail industry is shifting towards data-driven marketing, using growth hacking tools to maximize sales numbers through targeted advertising. Starting with big corporates and following through all the way to single-member companies. Consumerism is fuelled by our instinctively induced desires, now these desires have won a new digital companion catalysing our behaviour to embrace our side as hunter and gatherers. Watching the sequence of events closely – leading to the “brave new world” – we are living in now, we will notice something simultaneously inspiring as much as devastating. Without consciously formulating the goal itself, social media has engineered an artificial entity influencing our reality from start to end. Frequent users of social media platforms are served content and information determined by an algorithm optimized to captivate our attention and provoke engagement. This immediately impacts our thinking, feeling and beliefs. Radical (new) ideas, emotional pinnacles, fundamental values as results of that can all be allocated to the content we are fed. Following actions in turn are used to further optimize personalized algorithms resulting in gained efficiency catching our interests. This marks a full circle from

3 Y. N. Harari, *Sapiens. A Brief History of Humankind*/Yuval Noah Harari, Vintage Books, London 2014.

ideation to action and conclusion determined by an artificial self-improving algorithm, which has once started out as marketing tool to maximize time spend on social media.

3. The Limits of Human Cognition

Limits. The British anthropologist Robin Dunbar found a correlation between social group sizes and the Neocortex size. He formulated the hypothesis – later known as “Dunbar’s number” – which said that humans could not maintain social group sizes larger than roughly 150 people. Members of this social group would have to fulfil the following criteria: “people you would not feel embarrassed about joining uninvited for a drink if you happened to bump into them in a bar”⁴. This is another insightful testament, which shows that our biology limits the horizon we are capable of discovering. Probably much more narrowly than we would intuitively admit. At the same time, it gives a very plastic approximation of our cognitive diameter. We humans are limited, just as the human eye cannot see more than 10 million colours⁵, our heart beat faster than 220 beats per minute⁶, or run much faster than 45 kilometres per hour⁷, we cannot conceptualize limitless information. We have a start and an end, we live, and we die. This sentiment stands at the very core of our existence defining our boundaries, yet ironically encouraging us to excel at finding ways to overcome those set limits. Interestingly, Barret et Dunbar showed in later models that leveraging information and communications technology (ICT) can enable humans to break through this limit⁸.

Evolution. Elon musk, founder and CEO of Tesla and an array of other high-tech companies, also regarded as the real life “Iron Man”, has voiced his concerns about AI being a serious threat to humankind on multiple occasions. The core of his concern lies within his prediction, that AI will inevitably surpass human

4 R. I. M. Dunbar, “Neocortex Size as a Constraint on Group Size in Primates”, in «Journal of Human Evolution», 22 (6), p. 469-493, 1992. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2484\(92\)90081-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-2484(92)90081-J); R. I. M. Dunbar, *Grooming, Gossip, and the Evolution of Language*, Harvard University Press, 1998. See also: D. Purves et al., *Principles of Cognitive Neuroscience*, Oxford University Press, 2012.

5 J. B. Deane and W. Gunter, *Color in Business, Science and Industry*, Wiley, New York 1975; M. Komorowski et al., “The Artificial Intelligence Clinician Learns Optimal Treatment Strategies for Sepsis in Intensive Care”, in «Nature Medicine», 24 (11), p. 1716-1720, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-018-0213-5>.

6 H. Tanaka, K. D. Monahan, and D. R. Seals, “Age-Predicted Maximal Heart Rate Revisited”, in «Journal of the American College of Cardiology», 37 (1), p. 153-156, 2001. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097\(00\)01054-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097(00)01054-8).

7 Retrieved February 8, 2021, from <https://www.worldathletics.org/records/all-time-toplists/sprints/100-metres/outdoor/men/senior>.

8 T. Dávid-Barrett and R. I. M. Dunbar, “Processing Power Limits Social Group Size: Computational Evidence for the Cognitive Costs of Sociality”, in «Proceedings. Biological Sciences / The Royal Society», 280 (1765), p. 20131151, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2013.1151>.

cognitive capacities, and therefore mankind's future will be at some point at AI's mercy. AI evangelists argue that humanity is the bootloader for "General AI". An AI which is self-sufficient in its thinking, learning and decision making. The next step in the evolution of conscious entities. Looking at this, one might sense the tragedy in humankind's story. In the quest of overcoming natural selection and attempt to take place among transcendent beings reigning over nature, we undoubtedly are steering towards a potential future erasing our designated place in organic evolution. Although we might be seen as extended arm of mother nature's ambitions, there is still no denying that our unparalleled problem-solving skills might eventually lead to the creation of the next "species" in line. Smarter, more adaptable, more robust; superior. So, what does it mean for us humans now and the future? Is it time to stop technological progress and be contentious with the status quo? Should we start reflecting about our inherent societal incentives and value systems? Could it be that a step backwards is a step forward for humanity? Probably all these questions could be answered with "yes", and as controversial as they might be, they undeniably are legitimate concerns. However, it is highly unlikely, that any attempt of slowing down technological ascension can exist in any realistic scenario. The sheer glow of momentum, nourished by desire and reward, holds elusive blinding power, rendering the public consciousness numb to far-fetched concerns of hypothetical threat scenarios.

He will win who knows when to fight and when not to fight.

Sun Tzu, *The Art of War*⁹

While this sentiment is nothing novel to people engaged in this field, Elon Musk has an ingenious approach to tackle this (for now) hypothetical future threat. There is a saying along these lines: "If you cannot beat them, join them". Neuralink¹⁰ is a whole company dedicated to achieving this goal and finding a way to link the human brain to artificial processing prowess. The idea is to create a "brain machine interface" which translates biological thinking into digital processing and the other way around. This way the concept of human-machine amalgamation on an existential level completes its transition from science fiction to reality, lifting the limits of human cognition. In any case, the close examination of our current relationship to technology reveals interesting aspects to this idea. Looking at how the impact of mainstream internet and pocket-sized personal computers (aka smartphones) have already leveraged our abilities today, paints a clear picture of where we are headed. With humanities collected knowledge at the press of a touch pad, the deeply interwoven connections to technology can be seen as digital prosthesis supporting our walk through modern life.

So, AI is more of a friend than a foe?

9 S. Tzu et al., *The Art of War*, Vol. 361, Oxford University Press, 1971.

10 Available at: <https://neuralink.com>.

4. Data the Oil of the 21st Century

AI adoption. Over the last decade, the increasing adoption of AI in various fields of the industry has brought experimental concepts from research to real life application, solving real world problems. Especially, the advent of big data collection has enabled rapid improvements in AI applicability and reliability in many research and technical areas. Quantity and quality of data are well recognized as the two essential limiting factors of AI modelling, ultimately determining its practical value. One of the most controversial areas of the industry for exploiting big data is the health domain, which has likewise profited from advances in the field of AI. In recent times, the process has started to translate AI approaches into clinical applications. Although most approaches remain in experimental and piloting settings, some have reached the clinical work already today¹¹.

Example. The concept of a so-called “digital twin” has made its way from engineering into all fields of simulation. The idea is to achieve an accurate model of reality, and therefore being able to simulate any potential situation the model might face, enabling the prediction and consequently prevention of undesired outcomes. In respect to health and medicine this concept is particularly enticing for obvious reasons. Moreover, collecting personal data in all areas of life through tracking devices and software would eventually enable a par for par depiction of an individual, which would equalize the “Oracle of Delphi” on an individual level.

Potential. The information harboured in big data can unlock the full potential of what AI can be capable of. In the case of medicine, electronic health records (EHRs) are one of the most promising sources pursued in the digital medicine community. The reason for the great interest in EHRs is simple; in order to predict and possibly prevent disease events and trajectories, AI has to learn from data which precisely depicts factors contributing to health and disease. These do not only include clinical findings and medical examinations, but also individual habits, personal interests, and other confidential information about every aspect of one’s life. One could say the more sensitive the data, the more valuable it is for training an effective AI. Making this by nature highly heterogeneous and flawed data available for AI ingestion requires several cutting-edge technologies, which each in itself poses a challenge to solve technological conundrums even big

11 T. Bennett et al., “Accuracy of the Epic Sepsis Prediction Model in a Regional Health System” in «*AMIA Symposium 2018*», 2019. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1902.07276>; T. Deist et al., “Machine Learning Algorithms for Outcome Prediction in (Chemo)Radiotherapy: An Empirical Comparison of Classifiers”, in «*Medical Physics*», 45 (7), p. 3449-3459, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mp.12967>; M. Komorowski et al., “The Artificial Intelligence Clinician Learns Optimal Treatment Strategies”, cit.; S. Walsh et al., “Towards a Clinical Decision Support System for External Beam Radiation Oncology Prostate Cancer Patients: Proton vs. Photon Radiotherapy? A Radiobiological Study of Robustness and Stability”, in «*Cancers*», 10 (2), 2018. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers10020055>.

tech giants such as IBM¹² and Google¹³, have yet failed to overcome. However, ironically gaining access to such highly sensitive data often poses the actual mammoth challenge.

The dilemma here is that on the one hand massive resources are spent to create detailed and conclusive reports on the clinical trajectories of patients, on a daily or even hourly basis, – enabling understanding of the clinical status of the patient for the whole medical team involved in the care of individual patients and serving as the foundation of any clinical decision – but at the same time these enormous amounts of precious data are often regarded too sensitive to be analysed by third parties. Yet, the granularity of the documentation in EHRs can serve as invaluable pointers to understand the condition of the patient which is simultaneously paramount to train effective next generation AI/ML based services.

Having laid this groundwork of the potential of data, the main question presents itself on the other side of the coin: “Why is there such big reluctance of providing personal data, or else said, why has data ownership such a high priority?” What is that we fear or are afraid to lose? What is the driving force, which has let privacy become one of the biggest obstacles for research and the progress of novel knowledge creation?

5. Privacy Our Right; GDPR Our Bastion of Justice?

The idea. The EU directive Article 179 TFEU¹⁴ encourages the use of data for the purposes of research and advancing industry standards, generally advancing technology which could benefit the society as a whole. Unfortunately, the current trend sees regional legislation in many European countries enforcing stricter GDPR regulations, which obstructs unbureaucratic research with personal data and in some cases prevents it at all. One example is Finland, which can be considered to be a pioneer in many regards when it comes to societal challenges, and as such Finland has already achieved something, where many other European countries are still struggling with the ideation phase. In Finland, “Findata” was founded, a national Health and Social Data Permit Authority. Its activities are

12 GMT, “How IBM Watson Overpromised and Underdelivered on AI Health Care—IEEE Spectrum”, in *IEEE Spectrum: Technology, Engineering, and Science News*. Retrieved August 15, 2020, from <https://spectrum.ieee.org/biomedical/diagnostics/how-ibm-watson-overpromised-and-underdelivered-on-ai-health-care>.

13 H. Tang and J. H. K. Ng, “Googling for a Diagnosis. Use of Google as a Diagnostic Aid: Internet Based Study”, in «*BMJ / Clinical Research Ed.*», 333 (7579), p. 1143-1145, 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.39003.640567.AE>.

14 Treaty of the Functioning of the European Union, which establishes the European research area (Article 179 TFEU): “1. The Union shall have the objective of strengthening its scientific and technological bases by achieving a European research area in which researchers, scientific knowledge and technology circulate freely, and encouraging it to become more competitive, including in its industry, while promoting all the research activities deemed necessary by virtue of other Chapters of the Treaties”.

based upon the Act on the Secondary Use of Health and Social Data (552/2019) and its purpose is to “improve the data security of data materials containing health and social data and enables more efficient utilization of these materials”¹⁵. This is without a doubt a step in the right direction to unify execution policies on health data, which brings invaluable transparency for citizens and therefore creating trust in the process of data sharing. However, in practice current research projects which attempt to share data, especially across borders, have shown – at least for now – that the central institution poses a significant challenge for data sharing, since it applies a very strict interpretation of GDPR regulations. This of course must be seen in the light of its very recent establishment, still growing into its intricate role as Finnish data custodian. However, it considerably slows down and disparages research results.

Private. Privacy implies the priority not to reveal information which is considered private. It aims at keeping boundaries of ownership over personal information and institutionalizes our right to control what is public and what is not. Having this clear-cut definition in place, we need to respect the fact, that privacy is something deeply personal. Just as there is no doubt that religious beliefs are an exclusively personal dimension to one’s personality, the understanding of what private means for each person is as individual as our characters are. Having that said there are general concepts which find mainstream consensus, some more controversial than others.

Anonymity. So, is it our biggest concern to stay anonymous, unknown, and mysterious? That seems a little bit too humble in its claim. And while there is undoubtedly confidential information about us we might desire to keep to ourselves, it is plausible that the innate fear of being exposed and losing status in the social hierarchy, would eventually subside in a society in which all taboos are emancipated topics, to be discussed publicly. If the devil emerges from the underground and is allowed to live peacefully aloft in heaven, the devil once, is called an angel again. So, if we can rule out confidentiality as main force behind our pursuit to preserve privacy, what other motifs can take responsibility? Is it the fact that we are so eager to control what is known about us and which picture is concluded in the minds of others? Is it the sheer desire to be in control of the image that is perceived on the stage we call “society”? The despair that is created by an incomplete or inaccurate picture of ourselves, a picture which can never do the person behind the dataset justice? Much more than the concern of revealing something about us, is it the fear of being reduced to what is actually publicly known about us? There is a case to be made that the dissonance of what is known about us versus what we are composed of is a substantial intrinsic driver for the urge of remaining private. After all, one prominent example in recent years, which points at several serious issues with being publicly exposed as a new social norm, is social media. Significant increases in depression and suicide rates, especially in adolescents, have been

15 “What is Findata?”, available at: <https://findata.fi/en/what-is-findata>.

linked to an increase in social media use¹⁶. Two motifs can be identified looking at this problem: “misuse” and “curation”, both of which lead to a deviating picture of oneself. Discussing the array of influences of social media on the external and internal world, might lead too far, however we can deduce one important underlying principle. A misrepresentation of the “true-self“ appears to have exclusively negative consequences looking at the long-term and large scale of things.

Moving forward. Given the fact that participants in society are all subject of data collection, the argument can be made, that eventually the final consequence will present the situation that all participants will be revealing data to the same extend. This would, as a thought experiment, obliterate any attempt to use public personal information as differentiator in any form or fashion. Therefore more precisely, the actual question we might need to ask ourselves is: “Are we the sum of our collected data?” At the moment, we are unquestionably more, much more than what could be even theoretically collected about us. However, extrapolating the progress in technology and seeing the trends towards the concept of an “augmented-me”, at some point in the future we will most definitely not represent more, but probably less than what is to be collected about us and derived from those data sets. So, in the end we solve the issues of the present by betting on the future.

Responsibility. In a theoretic “open data Shangri-la”, we are living in a world, where there are no secrets, for nobody. The only privacy we preserve might be the ideas in our head, although future inventions such as before mentioned “brain-machine interfaces” might even bring transparency to the realm of thoughts. In any case, while a world without any privacy might appear more a dystopian rather than a utopian model of the world, we need to keep in mind that we are judging a future with the eyes of the present. So, for the sake of the argument, let us assume humanity is capable of adapting to this reality, eventually. As long as transparency is universal for all participants of society and we avoid running into an iteration of the “animal farm” ideology, this argument holds a strong ground looking at the progress made from humanity’s inception until today. But even with transparency as prime directive we will find certain consequences, which will tarnish the overall picture. Having transparency on our well-being, character, actions et cetera does not only enable measures to improve every individual’s life based upon those data, but also facilitates optimizing the mechanics of the world around us. This includes insurances adapting costs based upon our actual health status, job offers based upon our innate potential, governmental resources allocated to population groups to serve the reigning value system.

Where there is great power, there is great responsibility.

16 J. M. Twenge et al., “Increases in Depressive Symptoms, Suicide-Related Outcomes, and Suicide Rates Among U.S. Adolescents After 2010 and Links to Increased New Media Screen Time”, in «Clinical Psychological Science», 6 (1), p. 3-17, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2167702617723376>.

Sir Winston Churchill

Again, the sentiment might arise, that these kinds of practices undermine a truly utopian future, however would it be more ethical to ignore revealed differences?

Concluding this tentative review of potential roots of privacy incentives creates the impression that given enough time, many issues might resolve themselves and pose much more temporary obstacles, brought into existence by the immaturity of our society and boundaries of digital perception. However, arriving at the extrapolated utopian “open data Shangri-la”, we find new ethical dilemmas caused by the fact of omniscience. And as knowledge is power, we need to deal with the equivalent burden of responsibility. Who should shoulder this responsibility? If privacy is not the enemy, is ownership the foe to be blamed?

The axiom stands that without good, bad cannot exist and as simple as the principle might seem its applications are vast.

6. Loss in Control Needs Gain in Trust

Ownership. You are responsible for what you own. Personal data seems to be clear cut in that regard. However, should you be responsible for how the world interacts with what you represent? The current trend sees individual data ownership as the solution to privacy. The individual decides what information can be collected and gives consent at any given point. Therefore, he/she also decides on which purposes of data processing will be supported. However, the concern has to be raised how effective a decision is, if the basis for it was uninformed or misinformed due to its complexity, unfamiliarity or just sheer overwhelming nature. This situation can often be encountered when considering the overflow of data consent “boxes and buttons”, which pop up as sort of daily routine interacting with any data collecting application. A general decision fatigue can be sensed when touching on this topic of websites asking for consent to track information. Whereas this solution might legitimately shed responsibility to every individual, the real issues emerge, when data could be potentially useful for research and innovation. In these contexts, often consent cannot be collected, since the purpose of research can in many cases not be anticipated at the time of collection, not to mention historical retrospective data where privacy had not been an established policy yet. So, again we have arrived at a point, where one side has to give, one right has to subside in the face of another.

Asset. While we have concentrated on idealistic price tags of data and its potential, having collected all the arguments for the crucial character of data, the obvious deduction will be its tremendous materialistic worth to the parties interested. Imagine an author writing his/her biography and never being able to claim profits from sale; or models having pictures taken without receiving financial remuneration. A broken business model one would say instinctively. However, the status quo sees companies exploiting personal data for profits, without usually reimbursing owners financially. The concept that personal information carries

inherent value, is one that has entered the public consciousness only lately. However, while awareness will grow with time, the right measures to be implemented to create a sustainable framework governing personal data and its financial value has yet to be found. The fact that the value of data is largely dependent on its use compounds the conundrum of creating a fair platform for data exchange. Having all that said, ideas such as “big data taxes” or indirect “added value taxes” could account for profits gained from personal data exploitation and facilitate redistribution on a societal level.

Supreme good is like water. Water greatly benefits all things, without conflict. It flows through places that people loathe. Thereby it is close to the Way.

Lao Tse, *Dao de Jing*

Trust. Daoism favors the direction of the stream, to follow the flow, not stemming against the tide, but surrendering to the course of events, using its momentum to one’s own advantage, reaching higher grounds by tuning into the synergy of acceptance. Making data sharing regulations more sophisticated and complex might undermine the emergence of heavily needed trust in order to promote data sharing itself. Holding a bird in one’s hand too tight, will lead to suffocating it, never being able to fly again. With no room for trial and error, without the chance to fail in the attempt, how should we ever find confidence in trust as a part of the ruling regulatory framework? The potential that big data holds within is unparalleled but failing at making it available can diminish possibilities past redemption. Ultimately, the real issue to be addressed might not necessarily be how to fortify protection of private information, or how to monitor distribution of data more closely, but rather to find ways to promote fearless data sharing and increase trust within stakeholders. Trust into countries, authorities, companies, ultimately trust in each other. Efforts spent on further enforcing and overcomplicating regulations to make provision of data more sophisticated, might diametrically work against the ambition leading to the desire for privacy in the first place.

Looking at our history, there have always been inventions, so powerful, so impactful that it molded the future decisively after its adaptation. Gunpowder, nuclear fusion, internet, to name some prominent examples, are all inventions, which bear incredible destructive power under malicious intent, however it is undoubtedly pertinent to exploit their incredible potential for the greater good. Regulations are essential to avoid misuse and consequent harm, and misuse of data has the means to impact individual’s lives on every level from birth to death. But, if regulations become shackles of innovation, because we fear misuse more than we value its potential for the “greater good”, we are ultimately creating a deadlock for humanity’s path in this world.

8. Where Do We Go from here? Individual over Collective?

Dilemma. Beauchamp and Childress¹⁷ have formulated a framework which can guide one's decision process if an ethical dilemma emerges. When different moral values stand in conflict with each other, it is necessary to consider aspects of all affected parties and navigate to a solution which does the least harm, while maximizing congruence with situational moral maxims. The "Four Principles approach" by Beauchamp and Childress provide a tool to tackle such ethical dilemmas by identifying four general concepts to consider:

1. Respect of autonomy
2. Beneficence
3. Non-Maleficence
4. Justice

Autonomy. Facing reality, we might not be able to turn over innate fears and desires deeply rooted in our nature within a reasonable timeframe. We are finding ourselves in a period of time where the world has changed gears and is evolving at a pace like never before. Life has become increasingly more complex with continuous additions of novelty to our range of elements we need to interact with in order to maintain participation in everyday life. At the same time, self-determination and freedom of choice have never been more pronounced, pushing over responsibilities, which were once beyond the individuals' agenda. And while these developments are a testament to our progress as a species, being capable of maintaining more and more individual rights, all of this is simultaneously restricting our field of vision and clouding our skies originally reserved to highlights of the moment. In a society which is dedicated to the emphasis of the rights of an individual, we might have forgotten the benefits of an individual serving the interests of the collective.

The first half of life is devoted to forming a healthy ego, the second half is going inward and letting go of it.

Carl Gustav Jung

Beneficence – No "I" without "you". Implementing a data sharing framework which prioritizes open access over given consent would clearly serve the "greater good" over individual rights, per se. Those individual rights, which are a landmark of progress. One of the most precious goods humanity had ever been able to introduce. Having this in mind, we need to consider that individual rights are aligned with individual responsibilities. The responsibility to respect the rights of other individuals, the responsibility to contribute preserving societal pillars which maintain these rights, the responsibility to ensure future generations to live these rights equally. Ultimately, the responsibility to serve the "greater good". The

17 T. L. Beauchamp and J. F. Childress, *Principles of Biomedical Ethics*, Oxford University Press, 2001. See also the book review S. Holm, "Principles of Biomedical Ethics, 5th edn.", in «Journal of Medical Ethics», 28 (5), p. 332. <https://doi.org/10.1136/jme.28.5.332-a>.

“greater good” to confine suffering in this world to the least amount possible. Therefore, the “greater good” serves the interest of each individual equally, and helping others means helping yourself equally.

Non-Maleficence – No “us” without “I”. There is the constant contention between the Western and Eastern mentality. While Western values revolve around the individual, Eastern values highlight the importance of the collective. However, at closer inspection one might realize that both mentalities are simply two sides of the same coin. The lone difference lying within the emphasis on the angle looking at the same goal. In order to achieve sustainable affluence, it will be inevitable to infringe on individual rights for the “greater good”, while in doing so is securing the foundation of present and future individual rights. Further, there is a decisive circumstance to be considered: while developed parts of the world are slowing down progress by attempting to preserve individual rights through an inert framework of regulations, less developed parts are paying the major share for delayed innovation. Ultimately it breaks down to the dilemma of gauging individual versus collective wellbeing, while there is a certain urgency and obligation to move decisively towards the greater good.

Justice. Inspecting the dichotomy between “privacy” and “greater good” we explored limits and potentials, ownership and responsibility, regulation and trust. In the end, it is a constant balancing act between left and right, up and down, forward and backward. However, favouring trust over control and faith over fear will be a service we owe ourselves believing in a better future for all of us, the only future worth striving for.

Dealing with the situation at hand, recalibrating our direction, stepping sideways or maybe even backwards might be the only way forward. We are experiencing a time, in which we struggle to maintain control over the information collected about us. And while we are desperately gasping for measures to achieve a peaceful transition to an “open data Shangri-la” in the future, we are losing that struggle right now today, a struggle which is slowing down progress, diminishing tremendous amounts of resources and growing bigger day by day.

A manifesto for the greater good.

Simon Lin, MD
Science Department, Symptoma, Vienna, Austria
First Department of Medicine, Paracelsus Medical University Salzburg, SALK
lin@symptoma.com

Simon Lin (M) graduated from Paracelsus Medical University and majored in human medicine. He is a medical doctor by training and gathered research expertise while working on his thesis project at Mayo Clinic. Simon gained insight in different areas of medicine technically and geographically, during his clinical work in leading medical institutions in the United States (George Washington University, Washington D.C.), China (University Clinic of Tongji University, Shanghai), and central Europe (several University Hospitals in DACH Countries). Today, he is the Chief Research

Officer and driving engine of Symptoma's Research department converging medical and technical know-how into Symptoma's digital medicine solutions. He has gathered broad expertise in the field of eHealth and precision medicine countless national and international research & development projects. His particular focus lies on the application of novel data science-based approaches to enable precision medicine and transform the diagnostic patient journey.

Simon is a passionate advocate for outside the box thinking and strongly believes in innovation through collaboration.